

Southern California CSU DNP Consortium

California State University, Fullerton
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PROMOTING CERVICAL CANCER SCREENING IN TRANSGENDER MALES:
BARRIERS TO CARE

A DOCTORAL PROJECT

Submitted in Partial Fulfillment of the Requirements

For the degree of

DOCTOR OF NURSING PRACTICE

By

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ABSTRACT

Introduction: Cervical cancer (CC) screening or Papanicolaou (Pap) testing has successfully decreased mortality amongst women. National recommendations have resulted in published guidelines for CC prevention, including specific age recommendations that facilitate provider compliance with the conduct of these important health care screenings. Despite the availability of resources, access to CC screening (Pap smear) within the female-to-male or Transgender Men (TM) population is much less frequent as compared to non-transgender women.

Background: According to the literature, the failure of TM to disclose their sexual orientation (SO) and gender identity (GI) are often caused by factors such as provider discrimination, bias, and neglect. This in turn results in a patient-provider relationship where open communication does not occur, leading to suboptimal care practices. An effective way to address this barrier is to create a welcoming environment by integrating SO and GI into the encounter history, as well as in the Electronic Health Record (EHR), in hopes of promoting self-identification and disclosure.

Methods: This project utilized retrospective chart reviews to evaluate the pre- and post- implementation of SO and GI intake forms introduced at a Los Angeles based health care institution between the years 2014 and 2015. A population sampling technique was used to identify TMs who received annual physicals within the Primary Care Department between January 1, 2013 to December 31, 2013 pre-implementation and January 1, 2016 to December 31, 2016 post-implementation of these new forms.

Discussion: The number of TM patients who were offered and completed CC screening (pap smear) decreased from 62.5% (15 of 24 patients) in 2013 to 52.6% (20 of 38 patients) in 2016, despite the implementation of gender neutral forms and higher self-identification of TM patients. Results support the need for further training of providers on how to provide gynecologic care to the TM population. Integrating SO and GI forms within a healthcare institution are key first steps in eliminating and overcoming barriers, but are not sufficient as a stand-alone intervention to promote TM equitable care. What may prove to be even more critical may be the presence of an open, trusting and respectful relationship between healthcare providers and their transgender male clients.

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INTRODUCTION

Over the last 50 years, the early diagnosis of cervical cancer (CC) and subsequent decrease in mortality rate for women has largely been the result of Papanicolaou (Pap) testing (Saslow et al., 2012). Pap testing is the main screening method used to detect abnormalities within the cervix that are often associated with invasive CC (Saslow et al., 2012). The American College of Obstetricians and Gynecologists [ACOG] (2014) reports that the number of cases of CC has been reduced from the rate of 14.8 per 100,000 women in 1975, to 6.6 per 100,000 women in 2008. Of note is that the mortality rate associated with CC also decreased from 5.55 per 100,000 women in 1975, to 2.38 per 100,000 in 2008 (ACOG, 2014).

The American Cancer Society (ACS), American Society for Colposcopy and Cervical Pathology (ASCCP), and American Society for Clinical Pathology (ASCP) have published guidelines for CC prevention that recommend women have their first Pap test at age 21 and that women 21 to 29 be Pap tested once every three years (Saslow et al., 2012). Women age 30 to 65 are recommended to have Pap testing once every five years in addition to human papillomavirus (HPV) testing, as high-risk HPV is linked to CC (ACOG, 2014; Saslow et al., 2012).

Despite these national recommendations, access to Pap testing within the female-to-male or Transgender Men (TM) population has been found to be lower than non-transgender women (Peitzmeier, Reisner, Harigopal, & Potter, 2014). Transgender is a term used to describe individuals who have nonconforming gender presentations (Rachlin, Green, & Lombardi, 2008). According to Rachlin et al. (2008), TM may express their gender identity in a variety of ways, with some individuals who transition

from female-to-male. This means a person's birth sex was female, but she will now identify as male. Ultimately, TM will live their lives as men.

The identification of transgender persons in communities is often challenging, but is essential to target specific barriers to care (Gates, 2011). Data from the Centers for Disease Control and Prevention's Behavioral Risk Factor Surveillance System (BRFSS) survey found that approximately 0.6% of the US population, or 1.4 million adults, identified as transgender [Table 1] (Flores, Brown, & Herman, 2016). This data accounts for individuals who self-identified, although does not include the large number of people who are either afraid to self-disclose or did not identify as transgender in surveys (Gates, 2011). In an earlier 2003 study, the California Lesbian, Gay, Bisexual, and Transgender (LGBT) Tobacco Survey identified 3.2% of the LGBT population as transgender (Gates, 2011). According to researchers, these figures make up 0.1% of adults in the state of California as transgender (Gates, 2011).

The American Community Survey, a national population-based survey, found that transgender adults are represented across all racial and ethnic groups (Flores et al., 2016). The findings showed that "Whites" are more apt to self-identify as transgender, and that minority groups under "Other" tend to have less access to healthcare, lower education levels, reside in lower socioeconomic communities, and/or experience more sexual orientation (SO) and gender identity (GI) discrimination (Flores et al., 2016).

Table 1

Estimated Percentage of Transgender Identified Adults Divided by Race and Ethnicity

White	55%
African-American or Black	16%
Latino or Hispanic	21%
Other race or ethnicity (includes Asian, Pacific Islander, American Indian, Alaskan Native, Biracial, Multiracial)	8%

Transgender Men who have an intact uterus and cervix and have not yet undergone gender reassignment surgery, often fail to communicate this information to their primary care providers. Failure by the TM population to disclose their SO and GI status can result in an unrecognized need for Pap testing as part of an annual wellness exam. Many healthcare providers also fail to advocate for TM to have Pap testing, due to the misconception that they are at low risk for CC (Rachlin et al., 2008). According to ACOG (2012), many TMs have been sexually active with men at some point in their sexual history, thus potentially exposing themselves to HPV. In addition, HPV has been found to be transmitted by exclusive lesbian sexual activity along with other sexually transmitted infections (STIs), such as bacterial vaginosis, candidiasis, and herpes (ACOG, 2012). This necessitates that all women, regardless of SO and GI, should be screened for CC via Pap testing (ACOG, 2012).

Problem Statement

The late diagnosis or missed diagnosis of high-risk HPV types such as HPV6, HPV16 and high-grade squamous intraepithelial lesions (HSIL) have been identified in the TM population, due to inadequate pap screenings (Marrazzo, 2004). Incidental findings of gynecologic malignancies in the TM population have led to the need for

reevaluation of the processes used to identify these malignancies at the primary care level (Marrazzo, 2004). Cancers involving the cervix have additionally been reported during the female-to-male sex reassignment surgery, suggesting that gynecologic care is not occurring at the recommended frequency for this population (Urban, Teng, & Kapp, 2011).

Purpose Statement

The purpose of this study will be to assess if the introduction of new gender neutral intake forms within one healthcare facility has resulted in offering annual gynecologic screenings for the TM population, thus entitling these individuals to timely CC screenings like any other female.

The aims for this project are to:

- 1) Complete a retrospective chart review to evaluate pre-and post-implementation data of SO and GI sensitive intake forms in the primary care department of a large nonprofit medical center in the greater Los Angeles metropolitan area from January 1, 2013 to December 31, 2013 and January 1 2016 to December 31, 2016.
- 2) To note if CC screening (pap smear) was completed for self-disclosed TMs in 2013 before implementation of gender neutral forms.
- 3) To note if CC screening (pap smear) occurred more frequently for self-disclosed TMs after implementation of gender neutral forms in 2016.

Conceptual Framework

The framework chosen for this project is “The Process of Cultural Competence in the Delivery of Healthcare Services (PCCDHS): A Model of Care” by Josepha Campinha-Bacote (2002). This model describes the ongoing process health care providers use to work effectively with a population, while navigating within the cultural context of each patient (Campinha-Bacote, 2002). The five main components which make up this model are cultural awareness, cultural knowledge, cultural skill, cultural

encounters and finally, cultural desire. Cultural awareness is the self-examination and in-depth exploration of one's own cultural background to recognize one's own biases, prejudices, and assumptions. Creating educational guidelines for providers and staff to address identified barriers is an important step in decreasing barriers to care. Cultural knowledge is described as seeking educational foundation or background about specific cultural groups. Defining terms and pronouns sensitive to SO and GI to create an inclusive environment are effective ways to target stigma and obstacles to care.

Cultural skill is the ability to gather pertinent cultural data to provide a culturally competent physical assessment. An increased understanding regarding needs specific to TM reassures healthcare providers and staff that they are providing appropriate care. Cultural encounter is the direct interaction with diverse groups to modify preexisting beliefs and stereotyping. By continuing to serve this group of patients, providers can modify existing practices that are sensitive to SO and GI.

Cultural desire describes the drive of healthcare providers to become culturally competent. The integration of these components involves understanding the fact that demographics are constantly changing and can lead to disparities in health care. According to Campinha-Bacote (2002), the interdependence of the five components of the PCCDHS framework require that healthcare providers create a balance among these components as they interact with patients.

The PCCDHS framework has been utilized in several health care fields such as administration, research, health care organizations, and policy, as well as in the development of clinical competence in mental health, rehabilitation, and case management (Campinha-Bacote, 2002). Utilizing this model can help create a guideline

for primary care providers to use when working with the transgender population. This framework will assist providers in obtaining knowledge about the specific needs of the TM community. A culturally competent healthcare provider should be able to provide an appropriate physical evaluation; one which includes addressing the TM's physical, biological, and physiological needs (Campinha-Bacote, 2002).

Furthermore, the PCCDHS framework will help to identify factors that contribute to TM comfort in the clinic setting, such as a gender-neutral environment, intake forms that allow for disclosure of TM status, non-gender directed screening questions and the use of proper pronouns. These comfort factors can help to improve the overall healthcare experience (Unger, 2015). This PCCDHS framework will be utilized to develop a guideline that can assist healthcare providers with becoming culturally competent.

Examples of how this can be accomplished is by addressing educational needs of the provider by having healthcare organizations assess knowledge base specific to TM population. Also, assessing strategies for healthcare maintenance aimed at primary care providers and staff such as learning about specific pronouns will help gauge the type of visit a TM patient will receive (i.e. incorporation of women's health care specific annual screening). Once clinics establishes trust, the importance of maintaining confidentiality of each individual TM patient adds to the healthcare organizations inclusivity and in turn decreases barriers. By incorporating these concepts the culturally competent health care provider is more likely to dismantle patient care barriers, thus, decreasing the incidence of health care disparities (Figure 1).

Figure 1. Implementation of Cultural Competence in Primary Care to Decrease Barriers to Gynecologic Care for Transgender Men. Adapted from “The Process of Cultural Competence in the Delivery of Healthcare Services (PCCDHS): A Model of Care” by Campinha-Bacote, J. (2002). The process of cultural competence in the delivery of healthcare services: A model of care. *Journal of Transcultural Nursing*, 13(3), 181-184.

REVIEW OF LITERATURE

A comprehensive literature review was conducted to determine accessibility to standardized gynecological screenings by the Female-to-Male or TM population. The following databases were used: PubMed of the National Library of Medicine, Cumulative Index of Nursing and Allied Health Literature (CINAHL), PsycINFO, ScienceDirect, and Google Scholar. Initial search terms included: definition related to TM and barriers to gynecological health care and cervical cancer screening. Further classification of the search also included: SO, GI, gender pronouns, and gender neutral terms. Lastly, the literature search included an evaluation of studies related to gender neutral clinical environments, access to care, cultural competence and awareness, patient centered care, healthcare encounters, and strategies for advocacy.

The search was limited to articles published in the United States between 2006 to 2017, written in English, and in peer-reviewed journals. Since a search utilizing Google Scholar resulted in many articles, only articles published in 2017 were examined. Articles excluded were those dealing with the following topics: Transgender Women, gay men, bisexual men, women over the age of 65 or younger than 21, endometrial cancer, ovarian cancer, and breast cancer. Other exclusions were articles which included other gynecologic health screenings such as mammograms, colorectal screenings, and other general healthcare screenings.

Reasons Why Health Care Disparities Exist for Transgender Males

Health disparity is described as the failure to receive equal access to care and equal quality of care as that received by their heterosexual counterparts (Braveman, 2006). Disparity can occur at every socioeconomic level, gender, ethnic group, and

national origin (Braveman, 2006). It is important that once a disparity is identified, efforts are made to identify inequality to avoid barriers to care.

Discriminatory Practices

Individuals from the transgender population have experienced health care disparities resulting from bias, discrimination, and neglect, which leads to less than optimal care (Lockhart & Davis, 2016). With a decrease in access to health care, transgender persons have faced higher incidences in developing chronic illnesses versus non-transgender persons (Lockhart & Davis, 2016; Quinn, Schabath, Sanchez, Sutton, & Green, 2015). Unhealthy social habits, mental health issues, sexually transmitted infections, and increased prevalence of certain cancers (i.e. cervical and breast) have been identified as health concerns (Pelletier & Tschurtz, 2012). These are often overlooked along with victimization related to violence and assault. The best opportunity for identification of these health issues was during the health care visit (Pelletier & Tschurtz, 2012).

Studies have identified stigma and discrimination as barriers to care resulting in decreased accessibility (Cruz, 2014). Barriers to obtain appropriate health screenings included limited knowledge of screenings, perceived judgment from healthcare providers and staff, and lack of a clinic sensitive to SO and GI (Johnson, Mueller, Eliason, Stuart, & Nemeth, 2016). This caused the TM individual to receive less than optimal care due to their reluctance to disclose their designated birth sex, primary gender, personal identity, medical care experience, and demographic data including relationship status (Markwick, 2016). Thus, TM patients did not access preventative gynecologic screenings as often as non-transgender women (Peitzmeier, Khullar, Reisner, & Potter, 2014).

Research by Rachlin et al. (2008) showed that TM reported difficulty with accessing care, with more than 50% reporting denial of service due to transgender status. Over 60% of TM were uncomfortable disclosing health information, and more than 70% were dissatisfied with their primary care provider's general knowledge of transgender issues. The TM person who then experiences these stressors will likely fail to seek out health care, and in turn, will miss important health screenings.

Structural stigma can also affect societal perceptions of gender nonconformity, and in turn cause health disparities for TM. The transgender community had difficulty with access to insurance for transgender-specific health care; often having to pay out of pocket (White Hughto et al., 2015). In addition to the lack of access to health insurance, few adequately trained TM friendly clinics exist, which further limited access to proper care for this population (White Hughto et al., 2015).

Lack of provider sensitivity. According to the 2011 Institute of Medicine (IOM) report, the transgender population experienced more health disparities than their heterosexual counterparts (Cahill & Makadon, 2014). Implementing interventions to increase patient disclosure could help providers develop positive patient relationships and in turn deliver appropriate health care (Cahill & Makadon, 2014). Transgender individuals were hesitant to disclose their SO and GI due to negative experiences related to providers who lacked cultural sensitivity (Cahill & Makadon, 2014; Marcus Law, 2015; Quinn et al., 2015). According to researchers, health disparities caused by a breakdown in provider relationships indicated that increased knowledge is necessary to help providers recognize issues that can affect transgender health (Daley & MacDonnell, 2011; Markwick, 2016).

Historically, the term “homosexuality” was identified as a mental disorder in the Diagnostic and Statistical Manual of Mental Disorder (DSM-5) in the early 1970s. It was not until 2013, that the term was substituted with “gender dysphoria” (Barbone, 2015; Markwick, 2016; Winter et al., 2016). This term described an individual’s emotional and psychological identity to be the opposite of their assigned birth sex, versus the previous term described as having an attraction to an individual who shared their same birth sex (Barbone, 2012; Markwick, 2016; Winter et al., 2016). Providers who continue to use this older definition risk being perceived as one who lacks understanding. Thus, this limits the provider’s ability to thoroughly examine a transgender patient and understand their stressor [i.e. discrimination, homophobia, transphobia, and stigma] (Markwick, 2016).

Creating a Welcoming Environment to Improve GYN Care for TM

The IOM, Healthy People 2020, the Affordable Care Act (ACA), and the Joint Commission collectively agreed to include SO and GI in the data collection and in the Electronic Health Record (EHR) to enable self-identification and disclosure (Cahill & Makadon, 2014). Effective July 18, 2016, section 1557, the nondiscriminatory provision of the ACA, mandated that health care organizations receiving U.S. Human and Health Service (USHHS) dollars prohibits biased or discriminatory care, based upon an individual's preferred GI (USHSS, 2016).

Healthy People 2020 supported recommendations to provide gender neutral forms, collect data regarding health care experiences, improve provider knowledge specific to this population, and increase the availability of transgender specific resources (Lockhart & Davis, 2016). The Health Resources and Services Administration (HRSA) stated that adding SO and GI as a required component in an intake form can help

determine health outcomes by promoting culturally competent care (Conron, Mimiaga, & Landers, 2010). Both recommendations would allow health care providers to improve transgender access to care, thereby decreasing health disparities for this population.

Modifications in the office and clinical environment [i.e. insurance coverage of transgender specific needs, transgender specific resources, unisex restrooms, etc.], as well as maintaining confidentiality could promote inclusivity, and therefore prevent barriers to care.

Understanding gender neutral terms. Using the correct terms to describe transgender population was important when providing care (Markwick, 2016; Winter et al., 2016). While often used interchangeably, the terms “gender” and “sex” are different and it is important to consider when caring for members of the transgender population. Sex refers to a person’s biologic status, which is either male or female and is typically associated with chromosomal, hormonal, external, and internal anatomy. Sexual orientation describes to whom one is attracted (American Psychological Association [APA], 2011). Gender and GI is the characteristic assigned by society specific to men and women (APA, 2011). Certain characteristics of gender are viewed differently within different cultures, while sex is viewed similarly across cultures (APA, 2011). It is important for healthcare providers to understand the difference in the terms applied to transgender population, to build cultural awareness and sensitivity, and improve skills and knowledge (Markwick, 2016; Winter et al., 2016).

The most common terms to avoid when providing care are *transgendered*, *sex change*, and *hermaphrodite*; as well as *transition*, or *intersex person* (Cobos & Jones, 2009). In addition, defamatory descriptions such as *deceptive*, *pretending*, *masquerading*,

she-male/he-male are considered insensitive, insulting, and disrespectful of a person's identity (Cobos & Jones, 2009). These words only serve to dehumanize a transgender person and create a barrier to care when used by practitioners.

Gender neutral communications. Most TM patients understand the importance of gynecologic care; however, they struggled with revealing their SO and GI to their providers (Dutton, Koenig, & Fennie, 2008). The use of culturally appropriate gender neutral language sensitive to SO and GI with an optional self-identification portion in an intake form, using open ended questions, facilitated disclosure (Daley & MacDonnell, 2011; McNair & Hegarty, 2010). Integrating specific needs into existing facility policies could result in inclusivity and improvement of services and decreases disparities (Pelletier & Tschurtz, 2012). The inability to identify SO and GI in a health care facility could often lead to poor results in terms of health care maintenance and increase exposure to adversity (Conron et al., 2010).

Being sensitive to gender pronouns is an effective method to increase and build trust. For example, if a man is present, he should be referred to as he or him. Failure to address this in a clinical setting could lead to feelings of distress, ridicule or embarrassment (Deutsch & Buchholz, 2015). In addition, TM presenting with male names, dressing as men, and preferring to be addressed as men may fail to inform providers that they have intact female anatomy. The assessment of gynecologic health can easily begin once the provider is aware of the status of the TM's reproductive anatomy. This allows for proper education regarding the importance of CC screening participation. Awareness and use of gender neutral language will ensure that health care

providers deliver the most efficient and problem focused health screening office visit for TMs.

Gender neutral forms. Researchers believe that the best way to initiate communication among TM patients was to provide subtle changes such as providing gender neutral forms upon initial office visits (Dutton et al., 2008). Providing SO and GI data in the clinical intake forms and electronic health records could increase disclosure (see Appendix A).

The Fenway Institute and the Center for American Progress, an organization that strives to enhance wellbeing of the LGBT community, conducted a study which supported the gathering of SO and GI data in health care registration encounter forms (Landry, 2017). They developed gender neutral forms which encourage self-identification to help providers collect information about the patients' status [Table 2] (Cahill & Makadon, 2014). Gender neutral forms enables healthcare providers to deliver efficient and problem focused office visits for TM, by providing counseling regarding the rationale of screening and explanation of gynecologic examination to promote understanding and compliance.

Table 2

Sexual Orientation and Gender Identity Terms in a Patient Registration Form at Fenway Health

Terms to address SO	Lesbian, gay, homosexual Straight or heterosexual Bisexual Other or Don't know
Terms to address GI	Male, Female Transgender Man or Transman Transgender Woman or Transwoman Genderqueer Other Other or Decline
Terms to address birth sex	Male Female Decline

Promoting Trust Between Provider and Client

Researchers supported the need for providers to establish trust within the TM community to develop positive relationships during sensitive assessments such as gynecologic exams (Peitzmeier et al., 2014; Rachlin et al., 2008; Unger, 2014; White Hughto, Reisner, & Pachankis, 2015; Wylie et al., 2016). Routine pap smear guidelines should be followed if a patient has not undergone a hysterectomy. The need to know if a patient has intact female anatomy (ovaries, fallopian tubes, uterus, and cervix) is critically important to avoid overlooking the need for CC screenings. Various study designs were implemented to examine factors associated with patient discomfort in discussing health and wellness with a primary care provider. This supported the need to provide tools to reeducate providers related to gynecologic health of TMs (Bauer, Zong, Scheim, Hammond, & Thind, 2015; Bradford, Reisner, Honnold, & Xavier, 2013).

Provision of Provider and Staff Training on TM GYN Care

Updating or modifying clinical settings by providing education and resources to staff regarding the importance of screening among TMs show supportive measures to encourage disclosure of their sexual health history (Johnson, Nemeth, Mueller, Eliason, & Stuart, 2016). Some patients believe that they are at low risk for CC, which often leads to decreased participation in health screenings (Dutton et al., 2008).

Developing training tools or guidelines could decrease or eliminate provider biases, recognize transphobia, and increase knowledge and sensitivity towards the transgender community (Redfern & Sinclair, 2014). This guideline could offer several approaches to provide an effective gynecologic clinical visit. For example, providers must avoid assessments and examinations that are unrelated to the reason for the office visit; this can be addressed by having patients' complete health questionnaires prior to the exam (Redfern & Sinclair, 2014).

A review published in the *Journal of Obstetric, Gynecologic, and Neonatal Nursing (JOGNN)* stated that without cultural sensitivity and inclusivity, negative experiences may be experienced which leads to poor health outcomes (Zuzelo, 2014). It is therefore important to offer providers the tools necessary to assess and deliver appropriate physical exams, disease awareness and resources to ensure high quality inclusive care for TM population to prevent missing important gynecologic screenings.

Understanding that transgender persons have increased risks and difficulties supported the need to promote continued provider education (Johnson, Mimiaga, & Bradford, 2008; Marcus Law, 2015). Promoting medical training specific to gender based diversity and strengthening of provider knowledge could ensure that transgender

individuals have better healthcare outcomes (Daley & MacDonnell, 2011; Poteat, German, & Kerrigan, 2013).

Summary

Based upon a review of the literature, there is a need to create interventions that will break down the barriers that are contributing to missed gynecologic screenings in the TM population. Transgender Men are generally less likely to present in an OBGYN setting for CC screening due to fears of discrimination or judgment. Increasing pap screenings in the primary care setting is necessary to avoid a late diagnosis of cervical cancer. Providing gender neutral forms, revising current documents, and establishing an inclusive clinical environment are the suggested first steps in building trust. Educating providers regarding the importance of CC screening, being sensitive to patients during exams by assessing comfort level, and asking non-biased open-ended questions that pertain to care can be effective in promoting patient compliance and care satisfaction. A heightened cultural awareness, and the provision of education and training for providers and clinic staff about this population might help build trusting relationships and eliminate barriers that preclude recommended gynecologic screenings.

The development of TM gynecological care guidelines for the primary care provider is one suggested strategy identified in the literature that might result in improved cultural sensitivity, knowledge, awareness, and gynecological care for this population. Lastly, current research supports the need to provide resources pertaining to medical coverage, resources, and support systems for TM. Overall, these interventions tackle barriers to avoid health care disparities for this population. These proposed healthcare

strategies have the potential to lead to a more equitable and just treatment of TMs, offering them a quality of care comparable to the rest of our nation's female population.

METHODS

Research Design

This project involved a retrospective design with use of chart reviews to evaluate the pre-and post-implementation of sexual orientation (SO) and gender identity (GI) sensitive intake forms in the project medical center. Chart reviewed were those of TM or TF patients seen from January 1 to December 31, 2013 and TM or TF patients seen from January 1 to December 31, 2016. The goals of these chart reviews were to identify whether individuals who self-identified as TM or TF were offered a cervical cancer (CC) screening (pap smear) at the time of her or his primary care visit, and if ordered, was this screening exam performed.

Based upon a review of the literature, TM individuals often failed to disclose the existence of their female anatomy, which resulted in not receiving annual pap smears as part of their physical exam. In addition, providers treating TM individuals who had disclosed their SO and GI, still failed to offer gynecologic care. Transgender men then missed the opportunity for early detection or diagnosis of CC.

The use of SO and GI intake forms was introduced system-wide at a Los Angeles based healthcare agency from 2014 to 2015. There has been no formal follow-up to date, as to whether the use of these new intake forms have resulted in any changes in treatment or disclosure of TM status. This DNP project fell under the realm of quality improvement, as it was designed to identify whether the adoption of SO and GI forms within this primary care setting has resulted in an improvement of gynecologic care for the TM population.

Ethical Considerations

This DNP project was approved by the hospital institutional review board (IRB) at which the doctoral student is employed. A collaborative agreement was additionally established by the IRB at California State University, Los Angeles. This DNP project was approved as an expedited study by the two institutions.

Full disclosure of this project was provided to the key stakeholders within the primary care group who provide services for TM. Data extraction involved using approved ICD 9 and 10 diagnostic and procedural codes specific to transgender population and cervical cancer screening. Data did include detailed identifiers such as patient names, medical record number, or date of birth for chart review which allowed to extract the inclusion and exclusion criteria. Confidentiality of data was maintained, throughout the entire process by corresponding via secured e-mails, including the write up of the DNP formal paper via personal computer.

Study Setting

This project took place in a large nonprofit 528 bed medical center in the greater Los Angeles metropolitan area. This facility has five adult specialties, and more than 22,000 admissions, 7,800 in-patient surgeries and 7,100 outpatient surgeries annually. This facility has locations throughout southern California and currently services over 4,000,000 members, of which approximately 3,000 of its clients are transgender patients.

Transgender Member Care Service is offered through a multidisciplinary approach consisting of providers from surgery, internal medicine, gynecology, endocrinology, as well as psychiatry, social services, and case management. In addition,

the primary care service providers (includes family practice, pediatric and internal medicine) are all trained in providing medical services to transgender patients.

Stakeholders

Introduction to key stakeholders within the primary care service and the LGBT Committee guided this project, in terms of providing data for the necessity of guidelines specific to the care of TM patients. An initial contact was made with the Chief of Service (COS) in Internal Medicine (IM) and Family Practice (FP) in early April 2017. Another important contact initiated in early May 2017 was with the current Transgender Champion who is the Chief of Medicine in Endocrinology. In addition, introduction to the consulting biostatistician through the research department was made in early September 2017; the biostatistician provided guidance with data extraction to assist with chart reviews for this facility. Finally, communicating with the OBGYN Department Administrator helped facilitate positive working relationships with the main stakeholders whose support was essential for carrying out this project.

Sample

A specific transgender population was of interest to the doctoral student, which determined which medical records would be reviewed. The subjects were TMs who accessed healthcare services within the primary care department of FP or IM between January to December 2013 and January to December 2016. TM patients could have been seen by an MD, DO, NP, or PA. The inclusion criteria for this chart review was as follows:

- Clients who had self-identified as transgender male
- Were between the age of 21 and 65 years

- Had a scheduled health screening between January 1, 2013 and December 31, 2013 prior to implementation of gender neutral forms
- Had a scheduled health screening between January 1, 2016 and December 31, 2016 post implementation of gender neutral forms

Exclusion criteria for this chart review was as follows:

- Were post transition prior to 2016 (i.e., Phalloplasty or Total Abdominal Hysterectomy with and without salpingectomy/oophorectomy)

Data Collection

The selection of patient charts was determined by using International Classification of Disease (ICD) 9 codes (302.50 Transsexualism; 302.6 Gender Identity Disorder Child; 302.85 Gender Identity Disorder Adolescent/Adult; V76.2 Screening Neoplasm Cervix; V73.81 Screening Exam HPV) and ICD 10 codes (Z87.890 History of Sex Reassignment; F64.0 Transsexualism; F64.1 Dual Role Transvestism; F64.8 Gender Identity No Transsexual; F64.9 Gender Identity Disorder; Unspecified; Z11.51). Patient age between 21 to 65 years was used as a filter, based on the national CC screening guidelines. Pap screening codes used were (V76.2 Screening Neoplasm Cervix; V73.81 Screening HPV) and HPV screening codes were (Z11.51 Screening HPV; Z12.4 Screening for Malignant Neoplasm of Cervix).

The information collected included patient age, race/ethnicity, marital status, and provider information (FP or IM), from the Research Data Warehouse (RDW) maintained by the Department of Research and Evaluation. Additional data that was tracked was the number of primary care providers, number of patients seen over a one-year period, number of patients who self-identified as TMs, and number of self-identified TMs who received an annual pap smear.

It was anticipated that once a primary provider delivered care for a transgender patient, he or she would have generated a diagnosis of “Gender Dysphoria”, Transsexualism, Gender Identity Disorder (child, adolescent, adult) or “Transgender” and from there, start a “Problem List” that would state Trans-Female (TF) or TM. The ability to capture this TM target population would be possible simply by reviewing the “Problem List.”

These charts would then be manually reviewed to determine if a screening pap smear had then been performed. Exempted from this sample were TMs who were post transition prior to 2016 (i.e. Phalloplasty or Total Abdominal Hysterectomy with and without salpingectomy/oophorectomy).

Data Analysis

This project used descriptive statistics to identify number of primary care providers, number of patients seen over a one-year period, number of patients who self-identified as TM, and number of self-identified TM who received an annual pap smear. The researcher anticipated that self-identification as a TM would result in a CC screening at the primary care level. It was also expected that the implementation of SO and GI sensitive intake forms would improve cultural diversity awareness and increase disclosure by TM patients, if they were served by a culturally sensitive primary care provider. Through self-identification, provider exams would be altered to perform gynecologic exams when appropriate.

The overall goal of this project was to determine if a non-judgmental and welcoming primary /care setting promoted better gynecologic health outcomes for TMs.

Its intention was to identify whether the introduction of SO and GI forms resulted in annual gynecologic health care screenings (completion of pap smears) for this population.

RESULTS

The aim of this project was to complete a retrospective chart review to evaluate pre-and post-implementation data of SO and GI sensitive intake forms in the primary care department of a large nonprofit medical center in the greater Los Angeles metropolitan area from January 1, 2013 to December 31, 2013 and from January 1 2016 to December 31, 2016. From this collected data, the percentage of CC screenings (pap smear) completed for self-disclosed TMs in 2013 was determined before implementation of gender neutral forms. Chart reviews for 2016 could identify if CC screening (pap smear) occurred more frequently for self-disclosed TMs after the 2016 implementation of gender neutral forms.

Data was collected from the primary care department (comprised of Family Practice Clinic and Internal Medicine Clinic) as well as the Obstetrics and Gynecology department. The data collection process was limited to patients who had self-identified as Transgender and had been scheduled for their annual physical visits. The dates for gathering data were from January 1, 2013 to December 2013 and January 1, 2016 to December 31, 2016. Patients were selected based on age criteria recommended by the American College of Obstetricians and Gynecologists (ACOG) for CC screening (pap smear).

Limitations with data collection involved the project center's electronic health record called Health Connect (HC), which presently cannot differentiate between gender identities. Upon enrollment, the patient is typically identified with "name, medical record number, birth sex" and does not account for identified or post-transition sex. This means that once data was collected, a manual chart review was necessary in order to determine

which patients had self-identified as TM. One method to find this was to use a “Health Maintenance Modifier” in the EHR and add “Genotype Male needs pap” which signaled a “Pap collect” alert.

The total number of transgender patients (based on diagnostic ICD codes) that met the inclusion criteria for this study was 24 patients in 2013 and 38 in 2016. This was then separated out by department, provider type, and whether CC screening was offered and/or done.

Variables for Data Extraction

1. Medical Record Number
2. Age (ACOG Guidelines 21 to 65)
3. Race/Ethnicity
4. Sexual Orientation/Gender Identity
5. ICD 10 Diagnostic Codes (F64.0, F64.1, F64.8, F64.9, Z87.890)
6. Transgender Males
 - CC screening (pap smear) offered (V76.2, Z12.4, Z11.51, V73.83)-to be assessed in the chart review
 - CC screening (pap smear) completed
7. Provider department (Family Practice or Internal Medicine)
8. Provider type: Doctor of Medicine (MD), Doctor of Osteopathy (DO), Nurse Practitioner (NP), Physician Assistant (PA)

Sample and Demographics

Patients were from the FP and IM department, in addition to Obstetrics and Gynecology (OBGYN) (see Figure 2). Patients seen in services such as Endocrinology and Psychiatry who often manage the TM population were excluded, as they typically do not perform CC screenings (pap smear).

Figure 2. Total number of transgender patients identified from January 1, 2013 to December 31, 2013 and January 1, 2016 to December 31, 2016

Age

In comparing age between study years, there were more self-disclosed patients 21 to 30 years in 2016 compared to self-disclosed patients of the same age in 2013. There was a similar number of 31 – 40-year-old patients in both years. In the oldest age groups (ages 41 to 50, 51 to 60, and 61-65), there were lower numbers of self-disclosed patients in 2013 than in 2016 (see Figure 3).

Figure 3. Sample by age groups in 2013 and 2016.

Race/Ethnicity

For the 265 charts that were initially reviewed for this study, disclosure amongst TMs were divided into five categories: White, Hispanic, African American (AA)/Black, Asian, and Other/Unknown. There were no other groups represented within this study cohort. Other comprised of one individual who identified as Indian, with the remaining classifying themselves as Unknown (see Figure 4).

Closer analysis of the 2013 inclusion group of 24 TMs (includes two TMs seen in OBGYN), found 16 TMs who identified as White, two Asian and four as Hispanic. In the 2016 group, which included 38 TMs (includes four TMs seen in OBGYN), 15 TMs identified as White, two AA/Black, 11 Hispanic, one Asian, and lastly, five who mainly listed themselves as either Other or Unknown.

Figure 4. Race/Ethnicity of TMs who disclosed SO and GI in 2013 and 2016

Diagnostic Codes Used to Identify Transgender Patients

From the providers listed (see Figure 5), the chart review revealed diagnostic codes used to identify TM patients. These ICD10 codes were the most commonly utilized diagnosis used. In addition, the chart reviews revealed “preferred names” and more recently “preferred pronouns” being documented, based on what TM patients communicated to their providers during their face to face meetings and interviews. Also, important to note, as evidenced by the chart review, Z87.890 “History of Sex Reassignment” did not indicate post transition surgery but rather a change in GI.

Figure 5. Diagnostic Codes used to identify Transgender patients: Z87.890 History of Sex Reassignment; F64.0 Transsexualism; F64.1 Dual Role Transvestism; F64.8 Gender Identity Not Transsexual; F64.9 Gender Identity Disorder; unspecified

Completed Cervical Cancer Screenings

A further review of the charts that met the inclusion criteria illustrated what occurred during the visit. FP, IM, and OBGYN providers were separated out by “completed” or “not completed” to indicate if CC screening (pap smear) was accomplished. Again, 2013 was the pre-implementation year of gender inclusive forms which encouraged the option of patient disclosure, and 2016 was the post implementation year of these forms (see Figure 6). Chart reviews during 2013 revealed incomplete screenings, and while six providers (FP) offered CC screening, the exam was declined by the client. In turn, three providers (two FP and one IM) did not counsel or offer any type of gynecologic care, including CC screening. In total, 15 (62.5%) successfully completed screenings (nine in FP, four in IM, two in OBGYN) and 9 (37.5%) did not receive CC screening during 2013.

In comparison, the 2016 chart reviews revealed that eight patients (six FP and two IM) were counseled to receive CC screening but declined. Ten providers (nine FP and one IM) did not discuss gynecologic care, therefore CC screening was not offered. In addition, three providers (all FP) discussed CC screenings but documented that the patients had completed this within the guideline intervals and hence, were not due for a screening at time of visit. In total, of 38 patients, 20 patients completed screenings (eight FP, five IM, four in OBGYN and 3 completed screening elsewhere); this is a completed screening rate of 52.6% which is decreased from the completed CC screening rate in 2013.

Figure 6. Number of CC screening completed vs not completed in Family Practice; Internal Medicine; Obstetrics and Gynecology in 2013 pre-implementation and 2016 post-implementation

Findings Summary

A total of 265 transgender patients were identified based on the diagnostic codes used by their providers, once patients disclosed their SO and GI in 2013 and 2016. From this cohort, the patients were divided according to the target study years either 2013 or 2016. In terms of age, the highest number of TMs who self-disclosed in 2016 were between 21 to 30 years of age. The 31 to 40 age group in 2013 and 2016 self-disclosed similarly and were therefore offered and/or received screenings. The remaining age groups had lower self-disclosure representation for TMs who received and/or offered screening, therefore, received fewer CC screenings. Amongst Race/Ethnicity, total in 2013 and 2016 included all TMs identified in FP, IM, excluding OBGYN. In 2013, 73% identified as White, 0% AA/Black, 18% Hispanic, 9% Asian, 0% Other/Unknown. In 2016, 44% identified as White, 6% AA/Black, 32% Hispanic, 3% Asian, and lastly 15% Other/Unknown.

Twenty-four patients met the inclusion criteria in 2013, which comprised 17 (70.8%) FP patients, five (20.9%) IM patients, and two (8.2%) patients followed by an OBGYN provider. From this sample, only 13 (59%) who met criteria completed CC screening (pap smear), three (14%) did not receive counseling for screening, and six (27%) declined screenings despite provider recommendations. Two patient's encounters were seen in OBGYN and were successfully screened. Most of the patients were seen by an MD versus another provider (DO, NP/PA).

In 2016, 38 patients met the study criteria and were comprised of 26 (68.4%) FP patients, eight (21.1%) IM patients, and four (10.5%) patients in OBGYN. From this sample, only 13 (34.2%) completed CC screenings (pap smear), 10 (26.3%) did not

receive counseling for screenings, and 8 (21.0%) declined screenings despite provider recommendations.

DISCUSSION

Summary of the Problem

Late diagnosis or missed diagnosis of high-risk HPV (HPV6 and HPV16) as well as high-grade squamous intraepithelial lesions (HSIL) have been identified due to inadequate CC screening (pap smears) within the TM population (Marrazzo, 2004). The need to reevaluate clinical process to avoid missed screening opportunities at the primary care level are fundamental in avoiding future cancers involving the cervix among TM patients. Various ways to increase this is by providing an all-inclusive environment to allow for self-disclosure. In turn, the provider is prepared to cater his or her annual exam to also include gynecological screenings.

Examining interventions that promote a welcoming environment for this population within this study project medical center can provide insight as to how to improve the overall health of TMs. In addition to assessing the impact of implementing gender neutral forms, the identification of any other influencing factors that may affect health screening patterns among the TM community may occur by performing studies such as this one.

The selected PCCDHS framework by Josepha Campinha-Bacote (2002) describes an ongoing process for healthcare providers. The five main components discussed applied to this project in that the importance of cultural awareness, cultural knowledge, cultural skill, cultural encounters, and cultural desire all lead to identifying barriers that prevent disparities among TMs (Campinha-Bacote, 2002). Prevention of disease in the primary care level involved creating a welcoming environment to promote self-disclosure which could then prompt providers on specific health care needs for TMs who had not

undergone gender reassignment surgery. The failure to capture screening for TMs necessitated evaluating why some providers failed to provide the necessary assessments. Based on the PCCDHS framework, weighing all key components of PCCDHS frameworks worked well to highlight opportunities to address sensitive, but necessary screenings for this unique population.

Learning from the Study Results

A review of the literature found that providers often miss opportunities in delivering specific gynecologic cares for TM population. The IOM, Healthy People 2020, the Affordable Care Act (ACA), and the Joint Commission collectively agree that including SO and GI gender sensitive intake forms in a health care organization's Electronic Health Record (EHR) can increase self-identification (Cahill & Makadon, 2014). By providing gender neutral forms, this advises providers to offer appropriate care and to avoid the omission of key screenings for TMs. Since the implementation of SO and GI changes in intake forms in this study facility, the data gathered showed that there was an increased number of self-disclosed TMs who presented to primary care in 2016 versus 2013. However, the percentage of providers who offered and completed CC screenings (pap smear) was low (52.6%). Chart review showed that despite self-disclosure (albeit the provider recognizing TMs by creating ICD 10 diagnostic coding to reflect SO and GI), screenings were typically not offered. Explanations on why screenings were low could be due to the lack of experience working with TM healthcare issues amongst providers. Developing the appropriate next steps that follow the implementation of gender inclusive forms will be key in discovering dismantling healthcare barriers for the TM population.

Limitations

Conducting this study in one institution resulting in a small sample size may not be generalizable. Utilizing other institutions can provide a larger sample size which could provide a better picture as to what and where the issues specifically lay. This can pinpoint specific gaps in care to target barriers which then assists in creating focused training materials for providers.

Implications for Practice

The Fenway Institute and the Center for American Progress is the leader in promotion of wellbeing of the LGBT community (Landry, 2017). As discussed in the literature review, this organization provided recommendations for health care organizations, educators, as well as providers on best ways to increase knowledge to deliver problem focused visits for TMs. Simply by changing intake forms to allow for the transgender population to disclose enables providers to avoid missing key screenings. However, despite implementation of gender sensitive forms, missed health screenings still can occur, as evidenced in this study. Targeting providers in terms of assessing their level of comfort, knowledge base, as well as any biases are important factors to address if the healthcare of TMs is to be improved upon in the future. The Fenway Institute found that assessing the need for specific training would be helpful for healthcare organizations to address specific issues (Cahill & Makadon, 2014). Targeting the best ways to promote provider confidence with terms and pronouns collected from SO and GI data can dismantle some of the barriers to gynecologic care amongst TMs.

Other organizational changes that can enhance and support provider training is by establishing transgender champions, liaison, or resource groups. The provision of

resources/referrals, education on transgender specific health care needs all can contribute towards increasing provider confidence with this population. Literature has supported that the contributing factor to barriers is lack of training in collecting SO and GI information. Once successfully collected, what one can do with this information can lead to discomfort as it raises issues such as lack of provider experience, concerns that one may cause offense, and beliefs that this type of information is not relevant to care (Cahill & Makadon, 2014; Landry, 2017). Structured training is needed in all health care organizations to help providers understand and be sensitive to TMs healthcare needs. Offering transgender health education in medical school and/or residency for MDs and DOs, and in advanced practice provider education for NPs and PAs should be strongly considered. In addition to TM training for providers, patient education needs to stress the ongoing need for cervical cancer screening for TM patients, as six individuals (25%) declined screening in 2013 and eight individuals (21%) declined screening in 2016.

Recommendations

Although this study site has taken an initial step to provide a more inclusive environment for the transgender population, continued provider education is still needed to ensure that the barriers that cause health care disparities for TM patients are broken down. The need to provide continued training for providers can help ensure that TMs are receiving complete care during their annual health care examination visits. This visit is the perfect opportunity to provide counseling on the importance of holistic health care, which includes gynecologic care in TMs. A knowledgeable and sensitive provider can successfully counsel, and then ensure that the necessary exams and screenings occur.

Understanding that TMs have higher healthcare risks and difficulties as stated in the published literature supports the need to promote continued provider education and training. The Institute of Medicine (IOM) 2011 report suggested that transgender health disparities (which includes lower rates of cervical cancer screening in addition to other stressors) can lead to an increase in illness. The IOM indicated that providing an environment which promotes patient disclosure can improve provider and patient conversation, and in turn build a positive and trusting relationship (Cahill & Makadon, 2014).

Organizations such as the National LGBT Health Education Center by the Fenway Institute are excellent resource sites where health care organizations can acquire up to date training, as well as technical assistance in advancing overall healthcare for TMs. Integrating SO and GI forms within the data intake system in an institutions electronic health record are key first steps in meeting Health People 2020's goal to eliminate health disparities by overcoming barriers (Cahill & Makadon, 2014). Finally, having gynecological healthcare pamphlets in facility waiting rooms as a means for educating the TM population may lead to important dialogues between client and healthcare provider.

Conclusion

Awareness of a patient's SO and GI can lead to improved identification of healthcare needs, and thus, better health outcomes by the TM population. If we truly aim to support the IOM's mission of getting rid of health disparities, strategies that promote equitable health care and treatment for TMs must be put in place, and buy-in by the key stakeholders in healthcare agencies that serve this population must come about. Lastly,

we cannot underestimate the importance of the client-provider relationship. This healthcare relationship may prove to be the most important strategy of all, for attaining our goal of decreasing the incidence of cervical cancer in the transgender male population.

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APPENDIX A

Example of Sexual Orientation Questions

Do you think of yourself as:

- Straight or heterosexual
- Lesbian, gay, or homosexual
- Bisexual
- Something else
- Don't know
- Choose not to disclose

Examples of Gender Identity Questions

What is your current gender identity? (check one)

- Male
- Female
- Transgender Male/Trans Man/Female-to-Male FTM
- Transgender Female/Trans Woman/Male-to-female (MTF)
- Genderqueer, neither exclusively male nor female
- Choose not to disclose

What sex were you assigned at birth on your original birth certificate? (check one)

- Male
- Female
- Choose not to disclose

Retrieved from <https://www.lgbthealtheducation.org/wp-content/uploads/Collecting-Sexual-Orientation-and-Gender-Identity-Data-in-EHRs-2016.pdf>

APPENDIX B

Institutional Review Board
Kaiser Permanente Southern California

Approval Notice

August 03, 2017

KPSC Principal Investigator(s)
Maggie L Weiss, KPSC - Ob/Gyn
4900 W. Sunset Blvd
Los Angeles , CA

KPSC Co-Investigator(s)
None

Study Title: Promoting Gynecologic Health in Transgender Males (#11393)

Study Expiration Date: 07/25/2018

On 08/01/2017, a subcommittee of the Kaiser Permanente Southern California (KPSC) Institutional Review Board (IRB) reviewed and approved your new study until 07/25/2018.

In accordance with the requirements for research activities that present no more than minimal risk to subjects set forth in 45 CFR 46.110 the study referenced above qualified for expedited review under the following research category:

- Category 5: Research involving materials (data, documents, records, or specimens) that have been collected, or will be collected solely for nonresearch purposes (such as medical treatment or diagnosis)

Study Document(s):

Title	Version Date
Data Abstraction Form Maggie L Weiss	07/19/2017

In accordance with 45CFR 46.116 the requirement to obtain informed consent was waived by the IRB based on the following determinations:

- (1) The research involves no more than minimal risk to the subjects;
 - (2) The waiver or alteration will not adversely affect the rights and welfare of the subjects;
 - (3) The research could not practically be carried out without the waiver or alternation;
 - (4) Whenever appropriate, the subjects will be provided with additional pertinent information after participation.
- The requirement that written Privacy Rule authorization be obtained from study participants was waived.

The KPSC Principal Investigator (PI) is required to:

- Review the document entitled HIPAA Privacy Rule Instructions for Researchers available at http://irb.kp-scalresearch.org/5/HIPPA_Privacy_Rule_Instructions_for_Researchers.pdf
- Submit a complete progress or final report of research activities.

And if applicable,

- Submit for IRB review modifications to the research and/or IRB approved research documents.
- Submit Adverse Event report(s) according to IRB policies and procedures and consistent with federal regulations.
- Submit Protocol Violation report(s) and other Unanticipated Problem Reports according to IRB policies and procedures and consistent with federal regulations.

Sincerely,

Signature applied by Isabel M Sanchez on
08/03/2017 12:54:47 PM PDT

Armida Ayala, MHA, PhD
Director
Human Research Subjects Protection Office
Institutional Review Board

APPENDIX C
TABLE OF EVIDENCE

Table 1. *Health Care Disparities*

Purpose, Study Questions (Author (s), Year)	Study Design & Key Variables	Sample & Setting	Measures	Findings	Authors' Conclusions; Limitations; Appropriateness
To determine causes of postponement in primary care among the transgender and gender non-conforming group (Cruz, 2014).	<p>Quantitative analysis</p> <p>IV: 1) Reported designated sex at birth; primary gender identity (MTF, MTX, FTM), personal identity (transsexual, gender queer) 2) Medical care experience 3) Demographic data, relationship status</p> <p>DV: measured postponement of care via 3 questions (why they postponed care, could they afford it, possible disrespect/discrimination from HCP)</p>	<p>Convenience sampling utilized: Collected 6000 responses which provided >statistical power for analysis using, NTDS Evaluated data from Sept 2008 to March 2009</p>	<p>Used 2 logistic regression models to analyze data 1) Binary logistic regression model predicted any postponement to care 2) Multi-nominal logistic regression model predicted reason of postponement to care</p>	<p>Findings suggested that lack of provider experience, understanding of identity, state of their transition, disclosure of transgender or gender nonconforming are all associated with postponement of care.</p> <p>Findings also suggest issues with discrimination and affordability in terms of postponement in seeking care from HCP/clinic care.</p>	<p>Authors conclude the importance of identifying stigma and discrimination, which is created from lack of research practice and health care availability sensitive to this subgroup of people.</p> <p>By pinpointing barriers to cares, this would enable providers and clinic staff to create an inclusive environment among the transgender and gender non-conforming groups. The goal is to create a trusting relationship between patient & provider.</p>

Purpose, Study Questions (Author (s), Year)	Study Design & Key Variables	Sample & Setting	Measures	Findings	Authors' Conclusions; Limitations; Appropriateness
Purpose of the study was to identify how stigma can influence health care interactions between HCP and the transgender population (Poteat et al., 2013).	Qualitative research Grounded theory approach	Purposive sampling of 55 transgender people; 12 medical providers	Collected data (January to July 2011) via one time in depth interviews covering issues related to stigma, discrimination, HCP interactions. 2 CABs (Trans woman and trans man) convened before data collection began and again monthly however researchers unable to form CABs of medical providers due to scheduling.	Identified interpersonal stigma and discrimination: blaming, shaming, othering, and discrimination. Identified functional theory discussed stigmatization attitudes serve psychological functions however it does not address how to acknowledge how providers can understand issues to prevent health disparities.	Authors concluded lack of medical training specifically for transgender people due to social and institutional stigma. Authors indicated that with better understanding of stigma and discrimination this could provide information on prevention of health inequalities. It is important to provide a guideline for primary care providers. Being sensitive to this subgroup of women is important to build trust->resulting in maintenance of health.

Purpose, Study Questions (Author (s), Year)	Study Design & Key Variables	Sample & Setting	Measures	Findings	Authors' Conclusions; Limitations; Appropriateness
Aim of the study was to study perceived health needs of TM (Reisner, Gamarel, Dunham, Hopwood, & Hwahng, 2013)	Cross sectional mixed methods	June 2011 cross sectional quantitative needs assessment (n=73) and qualitative open-ended input (n=19).	Latent class analysis; 6 binary health indicators used to identify health issues: 1)depression 2)alcohol use 3)smoking 4) asthma 5)physical activity 6)overweight status	4 health clusters found: 1)depression 2)syndemic 3)alcohol/overweight 4)smoking/physical activity/overweight 2 factors linked to syndemic cluster: transphobic discrimination & avoiding health care Qualitative themes: personal health, community, resilience, protective factor	Researchers found that identifying gaps in health care of TM communities is address health care concerns. Important to identify TM health care needs by continued research to decrease health risk factors →↓future chronic diseases (i.e. cervical cancer).
To assess access to health care services and documentation and how it affects the LGBT community (Daley & MacDonnell, 2011).	Critical discourse analysis using gender-based diversity framework. 2 objectives: 1)Identify primary discourse related to access and equality 2)understand how discourse can impact LGBT communities and their access to healthcare.	Health service access: Canadian (Toronto, Ontario based).	Key word search covering, sociological electronic database, including medical, psychology, health and social science. Keywords specific to LGBT used: sexual diversity and minority, SO/GI, homosexual.	Five discourses identified: 1)multicultural 2)diversity, three counter 3)social determinants of health (SDOH) 4)anti-oppression (AOP) 5)citizen/social rights	Health care service access and equality was reviewed to assess Canadian health service delivery→ results supported need for gender based diversity. Health Canada and WHO supported need for integrating gender based health and policy research to strengthen their knowledge base→ leads to better health

Purpose, Study Questions (Author (s), Year)	Study Design & Key Variables	Sample & Setting	Measures	Findings	Authors' Conclusions; Limitations; Appropriateness
<p>Purpose is to gain understanding of sexual health among TM community who have sex with men. Aims of the study were to gather preliminary data to create effective sexual health programs and to understand relationships between TM sexuality and GI. (Reisner, Perkovich, & Mimiaga, 2010)</p>	Mixed methods	<p>May-September 2009</p> <p>16 TM participated; a qualitative interview and brief interview-administered survey was completed</p>	<p>Quantitative survey included:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) demographics, sexual behavior, drug use 2) depressive symptoms 3) generalized anxiety symptoms 4) internalized homophobia <p>Qualitative interview identified gaps in knowledge</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) gender transition & sexual development 2) experience with non-TM men (past 12 months including recent encounter) 3) perception of HIV and STD risks and social networks 	<p>Mean age 32.5 (SD)=11.1; white 87.5%; queer 75%</p> <p>Perceived themselves as moderate high risk for HIV/STDs, 43.8% had unprotected sex with unknown HIV/STD non-TM; 62.5% used internet to meet partners</p> <p>37.5% had lifetime STD check; 25% had not been tested (past 2 years)</p> <p>“Embodied scripting” → theoretical framework to understand sexual health</p>	<p>outcomes for LGBT population.</p> <p>This supports the need to develop guideline which targets HCPs and staff to create an inclusive environment.</p> <p>Results led researchers to conclude the need for integrating sexual health information including peer support, addressing psychological health, training for TM patients and HCP via internet delivered information to target HIV and STD prevention interventions.</p> <p>The need to examine sexual health among TM who have sex with non-TM is important to decrease sexual risk. Also, this increases the opportunity to reach out to this community to address necessary screenings including gynecologic health.</p>

Purpose, Study Questions (Author (s), Year)	Study Design & Key Variables	Sample & Setting	Measures	Findings	Authors' Conclusions; Limitations; Appropriateness
			Qualitative data analyzed with content analysis, emergent coding system used to create theme categories		

Note. CAB = community advisory board, FTM = female to male, HCP = health care provider, HIV = human immunodeficiency virus, LGBT = Lesbian, Gay, Bisexual, Transgender, NTDS = National Transgender Discrimination Survey, SO/GI = sexual identity/gender identity, MTX-male to other, MTF = male to female, STD = sexually transmitted disease, TM = transgender men, WHO = World Health Organization

Table 2. *Assessing Barriers to Gynecologic Care for Transgender Men*

Purpose, Study Questions (Author (s), Year)	Study Design & Key Variables	Sample & Setting	Measures	Findings	Authors' Conclusions; Limitations; Appropriateness
Identify factors that affect CC screening among the lesbian, bisexual and FTM population (Johnson et al., 2016).	Quantitative analysis Andersen's BMHSU-a contextual framework IV: CC history, knowledge of screening, history of CC, perceived discrimination of HCP/staff, SO/GI, demographic information DV: ↑ frequency of CC screening	Inclusion criteria: 21-65 y/o lesbian and bisexual including FTM with cervix Recruitment by use of internet-based, community based, snowball: contacted 300 groups and centers Convenience sampling utilized: Quantitative: Collection via 48-item Internet questionnaire (N=226)	Outcome variable: frequency of Pap testing (CC screening). Responders who self-reported Pap labeled "RS"; those who self-reported Pap >3 years or no history of pap labeled "NRS". Quantitative measures created by researchers subjected to pretest, face validity, context experts, academicians & lay persons to ensure applicability to the public.	73% of sample identified as RS. RS vs NRS felt more welcomed (70.7% vs. 42.5%, P<0.001). Difference between GO not statistically significant (P=0.506), there was a statistically significant difference between GI (P=0.041). RS were more likely to open about their sexuality. RS more likely to report sexual activity (93.6% vs. 81.1%, P=0.012). Higher proportion of RS reported provider recommendation of Pap test vs NRS (81.2% vs. 50.8%, P<0.001). RS reported good experience with Pap test (p<0.001).	Study shows the need for nurses to help create an inclusive environment for the LGBT population (specific to this project the FTM group). Limited research studies on CC screening among lesbian, bisexual, and specifically FTM. By identifying ways to increase the frequency of Pap smear screenings will aid in identifying patients who are at risk for CC.

Purpose, Study Questions (Author(s), Year)	Study Design & Key Variables	Sample & Setting	Measures	Findings	Authors' Conclusions; Limitations; Appropriateness
				RS vs NRS reported their "outness" to HCP (67.9% vs. 45.4%, P=0.003).	
To examine CC screening performance of LBQT. ACS guidelines used for comparisons to assess what drives participation in CC screening (Johnson et al., 2016)	Qualitative data collected. Andersen's BMHSU-a contextual framework Deductive-inductive content analysis used.	Convenience sample aged 21-65 LBQT recruited via internet and community events. Telephone interviews, open ended questions and online questionnaires utilized. Inclusion: 21-65-year-old females (with cervix) 20 telephone interviews; 226 responded via Internet; total 1231 qualitative responses found between open ended questions (internet). Participants mostly non-Hispanic white women.	BMHSU theoretical framework used to identify 18 factors and/or themes regarding screening performances.	Mostly non-Hispanic white women completed CC screenings. Divided findings: contextual characteristics, individual characteristics, health behaviors, outcomes. FTM found CC screenings challenging: +emotional conflicts between assigned sex and GI.	Study showed that overall development of an inclusive healthcare environment is key in facilitating CC screening. The need for updating or modifying clinical settings by providing education to HCP and staff specific to this population can help increase CC screening rates. Issue exists that found LBQT women professed to be at low risk of CC-this resulted in decrease participation on screening. Limitations include lack of studies that focused on CC screening behaviors among FTM transgender population.

Purpose, Study Questions (Author(s), Year)	Study Design & Key Variables	Sample & Setting	Measures	Findings	Authors' Conclusions; Limitations; Appropriateness
Purpose for study was to examine CC screening in FTM versus non-transgender women (Peitzmeier et al., 2014).	Observational retrospective chart review Key Variables: -CC screening in FTM with uterus/cervix compared to non-transgender women	Data from EMR collected by electronic query and manual review 5,232 patients (4,882 women; 350 FTM) from an urban community health center Inclusion: HIV negative primary care patients; age 21-64 with cervix (2012) Exclusion: HIV positive patients	Individual-level variable: determine factor associated with screening (sexual behavior); hypothesized factors that may be related to trans identity) 3 primary care provider level variables: assess patients' likelihood of being up to date Classification based on screening guidelines by USPSTF, ACS/ASCCP/ASCP	FTM less likely to be up to date with Pap tests. Lesbians/Bisexuals not significantly more or less up to date	Findings show FTM do not access preventive CC screening vs. non-transgender women. Findings show the importance to identify barriers to maintain health and wellness for the FTM population. Creating interventions to tackle these issues are necessary to avoid missing screenings. By focusing on maintaining health within FTM population in women's health can decrease CC development.
Examining gynecologic care of FTM transgender population (Dutton, Koenig, & Fennie, 2008).	Qualitative study. Face to face interviews using convenience sampling. Phenomenologic framework.	Purposive and networking sampling used for recruitment. Six FTM transgender ages 19-45 were enrolled.	3-part interview: demographic and health questionnaire, Norbeck Social Support, Heath Care Relationship Trust Scale	1)Gynecologic care perceived important 2)Breasts caused the most GI conflict 3)TM struggling w/revealing their GI to HCP	TM who were receiving gynecologic care were those who had developed relationships with HCP. Limitations otherwise show that most did not receive care.

Purpose, Study Questions (Author(s), Year)	Study Design & Key Variables	Sample & Setting	Measures	Findings	Authors' Conclusions; Limitations; Appropriateness
		<p>Inclusion: self-identified FTM lived close to researchers, >18 years of age.</p> <p>Exclusion: non-English speakers, cognitively impaired, <18 years of age, did not identify as FTM transgender.</p>		<p>4)Lack of gender neutral terms/pronouns Assessment found barriers for FTM transgender patients when seeking cares.</p>	<p>Breast exam caused high anxiety about disclosing their transgenderism.</p> <p>Language was the most noteworthy barrier-issues with HCP documentation regarding presence of vagina despite masculine appearance.</p> <p>Limitations point to pronouns used by HCP and staff (second barrier).</p> <p>Understanding these barriers HCPs can make changes to enhance a welcoming environment.</p>

Note: ACS = American Cancer Society, ASCCP = American Society of Colposcopy and Cervical Pathology, ASCP = American Society for Clinical Pathology, BMHSU = Behavioral Model of Health Services Use, CC = cervical cancer, EMR = electronic medical record, FTM = female to male, HIV = human immunodeficiency virus, HCP = health care provider, LBQT = Lesbian, Bisexual, Queer, Transgender, NRS = non routine screeners, RS = routine screeners, SO/GI = sexual identity/gender identity, TM = transgender men, USPSTF = U.S. Preventive Services Task Force

Table 3. *Strategies for Improvement*

Purpose, Study Questions (Author (s), Year)	Study Design & Key Variables	Sample & Setting	Measures	Findings	Authors' Conclusions; Limitations; Appropriateness
To investigate transgender populations experiences with their providers and evaluate ways to improve their relationships (Ross & Castle Bell, 2016)	13 Semi-structured qualitative interviews with those who identified as transgender	Interviews were between 30-75 minutes. The average was one hour. 11 interviews conducted via Skype or FaceTime, and 2 in person. Online option utilized for anonymity. Researchers had difficulty finding larger number of transgender in the same geographical area.	Thematic analysis used to find common themes 1)Braun & Clarke's six-step process which provided steps for data analysis 2)Owen's thematic analysis to identify repeated themes, reoccurrences, and themes identified by transgender individuals.	Data analysis results show improvement with transgender and provider relationship: 1)Change in provider 's communication behavior 2)Modification to office environment and e-health	Future research and practical and theoretical implications warranted for improvement for transgender patients. Limitations in this study was the small sample size utilized to gather data. Despite this, the findings show evidence that support improvement in relationships between transgender population and their providers.
To examine factors associated with transgender (trans) patient discomfort discussing health and wellness with a primary HCP (Bauer, Zong, Scheim, Hammond, & Thind, 2015).	Cross-sectional survey conducted in 2009-2010. Multi-mode survey completed online and paper.	Respondent-driven sampling used for recruitment and analysis vs. random sampling due to the "hard to reach" populations.	Weighted logistic regression model used to create prevalence risk ratios. This was completed by average marginal predictions for transmasculine (n=184) and transfeminine (n=172).	Approximately half of trans masculine and trans feminine with primary HCPs reported discomfort. Those who planned gender reassignment surgery most likely to report discomfort with providers.	Risk of discomfort in terms of trans health with primary HCPs associated with ↑barriers to care. Study showed that this was present regardless of having a primary HCP and/or universal health insurance.

Purpose, Study Questions (Author(s), Year)	Study Design & Key Variables	Sample & Setting	Measures	Findings	Authors' Conclusions; Limitations; Appropriateness
		433 transgender people >16 years old surveyed; 356 had HCPs. 392 completed survey via online; 41 completed survey on paper: both had identical version.		<p>Greater perceived primary HCP knowledge re transgender issues associated with increased trust.</p> <p>Trans feminine 2.26x as likely vs. trans masculine 1.61x as likely to report discomfort.</p> <p>Previously married; higher education associated with ↑ risk of discomfort with trans feminine and ↓ risk with trans masculine.</p>	<p>Results were unclear if discomfort could apply to HCPs in “walk in” clinics or nurse practitioners. Also results did not indicate if a previous negative experiences affected current interactions with primary HCPs.</p> <p>Limitation in this study was lack of clarification regarding examination. Did the primary HCP refuse to examine certain body parts because the patient was trans or was that examination not relevant to the chief complaint?</p> <p>Being able to identify specific needs for the transgender population allows for better quality of care in terms of compliance.</p>

Purpose, Study Questions (Author (s), Year)	Study Design & Key Variables	Sample & Setting	Measures	Findings	Authors' Conclusions; Limitations; Appropriateness
Examining disclosure of SO/GI by LGBQ people to their HCP (Marcus Law, 2015).	Qualitative descriptive analysis Created themes by utilizing iterative coding, comparing, and grouping data 1-on-1 semi-structured telephone interview	LGBQ (self-identified) adults (age 18+) with experiences of HCPs (within 5 yrs). Recruited in Toronto Canada	Initial coding structure measured issues experienced regarding disclosure to HCP. Initial codes evolved → data analysis reviewed in tandem w/collection of data. Purposive investigation → identified new and existing codes which identified limitations Final analysis → identified thematic structure by iterative relating and grouped codes	3 main themes identified: 1) Disclosure to HCP was as challenging as coming out to family/friends 2) Therapeutic relationship = ↓ difficulty in disclosure to SO/GI 3) Purposeful recognition by HCP of dominant heteronormative value system = strong patient and HCP relationship	Authors found that improving HCP recognition of their heteronormative value system & structural heterosexual hegemony can ↑ HCP competence in treating LGBQ. Assessing baseline knowledge and providing guidelines for HCP can enhance patient and provider relationships. ↑ disclosure = ↑ health care and outcomes.
Examining an association between transgender related discrimination in terms of social determinants of health and their personal experiences (Bradford, Reisner, Honnold, & Xavier, 2013).	Used a 1 time cross sectional quantitative survey. Paper and an online questionnaire IV (of interest): sociodemographic characteristics; gender transition; access to care and needs; gender-based violence; HIV, interpersonal factors	Purposive sampling methods; included venue based strategies and informal peer network for recruitment Sept 2005 to July 2006: 350 participants out of 387 respondents were chosen in the	Multivariate logistic regression models along with generalized estimating equations (online survey vs. paper survey).	N=143 41% experienced transgender related discrimination. Factors included: geographic context, gender (FTM vs MTF), low socioeconomic status, racial/ethnic minority, lack of insurance, transition indicators, health care needs that are unable to receive (hormone and mental therapy), history of violence, smoking/alcohol abuse, family and community support.	Authors found that transgender Virginians reported discrimination in health care necessitating improvement with training among healthcare workers as well as improving access to service. The significance of creating a teaching

Purpose, Study Questions (Author(s), Year)	Study Design & Key Variables	Sample & Setting	Measures	Findings	Authors' Conclusions; Limitations; Appropriateness
		<p>final analysis (229 MTF, 121 FTM).</p> <p>Respondents were from 136 cities and counties in Virginia (total 44%)</p> <p>3 criteria: identified as transgender; age 18 or older; residents of or attend school in Virginia.</p>			<p>tool or guideline for HCPs can help decrease and/or eliminate discrimination.</p>

Note: FTM = female to male, HCP = health care provider, LGBQ = Lesbian, Gay, Bisexual, Queer, SO/GI = sexual identity/gender identity, MTF = male to female.